

SMART CLOUD STORAGE USING FACE RECOGNITION

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Abstract -Data security and identity confirmation are critical elements in modern digital society, given the rapidly-growing impact that cloud computing has had on data storage. Unauthorized data access can cause severe privacy violations and negatively impact businesses - often causing sensitive customer information to be lost or changed. This research paper presents an advanced intelligent Smart Cloud Storage system with a highly effective Two-Factor Authentication (2FA) based on a facial recognition pipeline. It achieves this by utilizing an intelligent fallback detection scheme based on multiple backends, with the first level of detection having a fallback level that prioritizes the RetinaFace detection system - providing greater reliability throughout this phase of the authentication process. Depending on which biometric feature sets are being used, both FaceNet's and GhostFaceNet's use of specific distance metrics for feature validation guarantee high levels of accuracy and context-awareness. All of the aforementioned characteristics will be combined in a new soft-voting ensemble architecture known as "Crop Once, Embed Everywhere", allowing for both increased accuracy and speed when processing the full 2FA authentication pipeline. The entire process has been validated using the Labeled Faces in the Wild (LFW) dataset, generating performance benchmarks for each architecture and experiment performed. Findings show that FaceNet has an average identification accuracy of 98.85% at peak training time, while SFace has proven to be one of the fastest architectures with a PPS rating of 21.36 frames per second (FPS) This approach provides an effective method for quickly comparing known data against new data while providing verification accuracy of 96.5% and having low error rates of 3% during training verification tasks. In addition, in order to provide the operational transparency requested by the customer, the system includes a visual diagnostic dashboard

that allows for real-time debugging of authentication failures, by providing structural similarity and embedding quality calculations.

Key Words: — *Secure Cloud Storage, Two-Factor Authentication (2FA), Biometric Access Control, Facial Recognition, Deep Learning, Multi-Model Ensemble, Soft-Voting, Equal Error Rate (EER), Structural Similarity (SSIM), Feature Embedding Extraction* .

1.INTRODUCTION

As the number of cloud storage services continues to grow exponentially, their resulting increase in user authentication security needs has prompted researchers and practitioners to investigate different types of biometric methodologies. The traditional use of text-based passwords for user authentication is vulnerable to phishing attacks, brute force attacks, and credential stuffing, resulting in many examining various forms of biometric authentication. Face recognition is now available for use on commodity hardware due to recent advances in deep convolutional neural networks (CNN's), providing an authentication signal that is both difficult to replicate and frictionless.

In selecting which face recognition system to utilize there exists a trade-off between valid accuracy metrics such as Equal Error Rate (EER) and Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC) versus inference latency and hardware restrictions. Additionally, failure modes that are unique to biometric systems exist; the False Acceptance Rate (FAR) or False Rejection Rate (FRR) of the biometric system have both security and usability implications when determining which face recognition system to use. If a cloud storage application were to erroneously grant access to an attacker (high FAR) it would result in a security

incident; conversely, if the facial recognition application repeatedly rejects the genuine user (high FRR) it would negatively impact the user experience.

This project has made four major contributions. First, we developed a comprehensive and secure cloud storage solution that supports facial recognition logins, as well as multilingual registration and liveness detection. It also provides AES-128 encryption for file storage. Second, we perform a detailed analysis of how four matching algorithms (FaceNet, ArcFace, GhostFaceNet, and SFace) perform against each other and how they work when paired as well as against individual faces using the LFW dataset having been evaluated by three different researchers. Third, we designed and built a soft voting ensemble, or group, that produces higher accuracy-lower EER than any individual matching model included in this comparison. Finally, we have created a reproducible benchmarking system through which we produce EER optimal thresholds and distance metrics

II. RELATED WORK

Many researchers have been implementing face recognition in authentication systems based on single-model architectures. An example is a Secure Online Voting System Using Face Recognition Technology, which found a 90% overall success rate [1]. As this example illustrates, while biometric authentication can be used as a form of identification, accuracy is influenced by various factors, such as changes in lighting, head position and image quality. Because the system used only one type of face recognition model, it was less robust than other systems would have been for real-world applications, so additional methods for securing accounts are necessary.

Deng et al. [2] created ArcFace—a deep learning-based approach to face recognition that leverages an Additive Angular Margin Loss (AAM-Loss) to improve the discriminability of features between different faces. This method has delivered state-of-the-art performance across numerous benchmark datasets and is one of the most popular architecture choices for face recognition. Despite this, in a thorough assessment completed by Chowdhury et al. [3], ArcFace returned an Area Under Curve (AUC) of 0.6894 on the CPLFW dataset, which contains large amounts of pose variation, and an AUC of 0.6177 on the QMUL-SurvFace surveillance dataset, suggesting that there is significant potential for performance loss across many real-world settings.

Alansari et al. [4] proposed the Ghost bottleneck layer for face recognition and achieved 96.83% accuracy on the CFP-FP benchmark as well as an accuracy of 95.6% on the CA-LFW dataset while requiring far fewer computational resources than conventional deep neural networks. Nevertheless, the lightweight design of GhostFaceNets places emphasis on inference speed rather than verification robustness; that said, they are appropriate for use in resource-constrained environments but may not perform well as a standalone, highly secure means of authenticating users.

Li et al. [5] proposed SFace with a Sigmoid-Constrained Hypersphere Loss function to stabilize optimization and improve feature representation during training. SFace has demonstrated strong throughput and efficient inference; thus, it is suitable for real-time applications. However, the results of benchmarked evaluations indicate that there can be performance decreases for SFace given certain challenging

circumstances. In fact, while SFace performed well with AUC = 0.7078, SFace outperformed both FaceNet and ArcFace on the QMUL-SurvFace data set (out-performing FaceNet and ArcFace across all data sets cannot be attributed to any one of these three models).

The web-based authentication system described, which uses MTCNN for face detection, FaceNet embeddings and LinearSVC classifiers, had around a 95% successful identification rate [6]. However, the system does not incorporate liveness detection capabilities and has not been tested in any significant detail across a variety of natural environments, leaving it exposed to spoofing and issues with real-world deployment.

Further comparison studies support the limitations of single-model implementations. For example, [7] compared the success rates of ArcFace, FaceNet, and FaceNet512 with an Indonesian facial data set and found the success rate of ArcFace (87.8%) and FaceNet (92.1%) were quite different. Showing that different populations and data domains can introduce a significant difference in model effectiveness, resulting in problems with generalisation.

Ensemble learning is a method that holds promise in overcoming the shortcomings related to performance in biometric authentication. The multimodal authentication system created by Abbaas and Serpen [8], was based on the fusing of face and voice data using an ensemble to validate the two biometric modalities. The result was that the system had good metrics across a variety of test measures indicating that using classifier fusion on different biometric modalities is an effective approach in improving biometric authentication performance. However, this particular approach was based solely and exclusively on fusing different biometric modalities rather than fusing various face recognition system architectures within one biometric modality.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Streamlit is proposed as framework for building multi-layered web applications. There are four exposed components in the presentation layer: Registration, Authentication, File Management, and Two Benchmarking Dashboards. The basis of the face recognition application is the Face Recognition Engine Layer, which wraps the DeepFace library for face detection, embedding extraction, and distance computation. A Persistent Storage Layer manages files as well as face embeddings.

Fig. 1

architecture of the Smart Cloud Storage system.

A. Face Detectors

The selected model will determine which back-end face detection engine to use. FaceNet and ArcFace models are based upon the RetinaFace face detector as they offer greater accuracy (but slower speed) than these other models. GhostFaceNet and SFace use the OpenCV Haar-cascade detector as they require lower latency when deployed in production. An intelligent failover mechanism from one back-end to the next (RetinaFace > OpenCV > MTCNN > MediaPipe) has been implemented to ensure robust face recognition.

B. Face Distance Metric

FaceNet and ArcFace face embeddings are compared using the L2 euclidean distance metric; this method is used because it aligns with the training intent of these models. GhostFaceNet and SFace embeddings are compared with the cosine similarity metric; these metrics are invariant to the size of the embedding and more compatible with the angular loss objectives used during their training. The EER-based optimal distance thresholds are tuned on a per-model basis using the LFW training set: FaceNet = 0.40, ArcFace = 0.68, GhostFaceNet = 0.65, SFace = 0.593.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The Smart Cloud Storage System uses biometric facial recognition and cloud-based file management to provide secure two-factor authentication (2FA). The system is built with Python and Streamlit, utilizing the DeepFace framework for facial recognition capabilities. The development of this system consists of the following

A. User Registration

During the registration process, the user submits a images of their face. This image will go through the following: face detection, quality measurement (brightness, contrast, blur variance), and embedding extraction. The quality score is weighted as follows: $0.25 \times \text{Brightness} + 0.25 \times \text{Contrast} + 0.35 \times \text{Blur} + 0.15 \times \text{Size} = 100$. Any images that receive a quality score below 50/100 will be denied, and the user will

receive an explanation about why they must submit a new picture. All accepted embeddings are stored with associated metadata.

B. User Authentication

The authentication phase will use a querying database in the same way that the registration process did. The facial image being queried will go through facial detection and embedding extraction and use the same modelling/implementation as used in the user registration phase to maintain a consistent embedding space. Once extracted for the querying image, the minimum distance from all stored embeddings matching the queried person's identity will be compared to a threshold calibrated to equal error rates (EER) to determine whether the person is who they say they are.

Fig Registration and Authentication Dataflow

C. Cloud Storage and Two-Factor Authentication Workflow

Through cloud-based file storage and indexing, the Smart Cloud Storage system incorporates two-factor authentication (2FA) using facial recognition technology to create a secure process for logging into and accessing files. When a user enters an existing username and password, they are authenticated via the system by using the same method of authentication as other users of the Smart Cloud Storage system. When the username and password have been approved, the user is prompted to take a live image of their face using a webcam or camera-equipped mobile device.

The face recognition model chosen to verify the user's identity is used to perform face detection, image alignment, and creation of the biometric template for the user after an image has been captured by the webcam. The biometric template generated from the captured image of the user will then be compared to the biometric template created during the registration of the user. The distance metrics and thresholds for face verification will be defined by the model used for face recognition, with the use of EER as an additional characteristic threshold. Once the username/password validation has been completed and the facial biometric template has been verified, the user is granted access to the Smart Cloud Storage.

Once the authentication process is complete, the user will have full access to the cloud storage services offered by the Smart Cloud Storage system, including the ability to upload, download, view, and delete files. Each user has dedicated

storage space so that data is separated from other users of the Smart Cloud Storage system. The Smart Cloud Storage system logs the results of the authentication at the time of access, as well as the distances of the verification compared to the biometric template, response time of the face recognition and timestamps, for the purpose of monitoring performance and auditing users of the system. The combined workflow of file storage and biometric verification creates a secure and efficient solution for secure user authentication and controlled access to cloud-based resources.

Fig User Authentication Framework

D. Benchmarking Pipeline

The Benchmarking Pipeline is being used to benchmark all models against a common dataset and provides a framework for evaluating performance against known metrics for two sets of images known as pairs (identified as matched or unmatched) to ensure consistency in evaluation methodology. For each model evaluated match and unmatched pairs are created using the same pair creation process defined in the LFW benchmark documentation. To optimise performance, only one detection of the same face is needed; therefore all images are detected

once and the corresponding face crop is created and then provided to every model, thus minimising the cost of detection over all models. The evaluation of each model includes: accuracy, equal error rate (EER), false acceptance rate (FAR), false rejection rate (FRR), receiver operating characteristic (ROC) – area under the curve (AUC), F1 score, mean inference time in milliseconds and frames per second (FPS). The EER is determined by the intersection of the FAR and FRR on the ROC curve and therefore provides a target-independent baseline for comparison between models under evaluation.

D. Soft-Voting

Soft-Voting is the methodology used to create the Ensemble, which is comprised of combining FaceNet and SFace scores using a soft-voting mechanism normalised between 0 and 1 for the individual model as distance or similarity measures, and then combines individual model normalised scores using an average on the normalised score to create a single soft-voting measure to determine a match. The result of combining distance or similarity measures in this way allows for a direct comparison across models with different distance or similarity measure scales. If the combined soft-voting measure is <0.5 , then a match is identified. This approach, known as Crop Once Embed Everywhere, simply reuses the detected crop from the first detection and applies the detected crop to each model separately, and thus results in decreased overall inference times as compared to performing the detection separately for each model.

V. RESULTS

The implemented system successfully demonstrates its capabilities. The FaceNet-SFace ensemble was evaluated as the principal authentication medium for the Smart Cloud Storage. This ensemble structure utilizes the Crop Once, Embed Everywhere approach where a singular face recognition detection will be completed and then reused across both the face recognition systems. This reduces compute overhead but maintains the complimentary (FaceNet/SFace) capabilities of each algorithm.

The training data set yielded an accuracy of 96.50% with an EER of 3.00% (FAR=1.00%, FRR=6.00%), thus providing strong separation of true to impostor users and reinforcing the appropriateness of the ensemble structure for secure authenticating applications. The testing data set yielded an accuracy of 92.50% with an EER of 9.00% (FAR=1.00%, FRR=14.00%). While there was a moderate decrease in performance on the previously unseen testing data set, FAR's were still at an extremely low level. From the perspective of cloud-security, the most important aspect of a security method is maintaining a low FAR. When a false positive occurs, it may allow unauthorized access to sensitive cloud assets.

The matching distances on average stayed pretty much the same between the training and testing data sets (1.0107 vs 1.0163) which suggests that there was consistency demonstrated by the fusion model. The low standard deviation indicates that the ensemble generated consistent verification scores for each of the users being tested. On the whole, this particular ensemble exhibits that the combination of FaceNet's ability to verify match and SFace's ability to provide fast verification through computation create a viable authentication mechanism that can serve to increase security in the cloud storage while providing adequate response times.

Table -1: Pair Verification Performance Comparison on LFW Dataset

Model	Train Configuration		Test Configuration		Metric	Train Configuration	Test Configuration
	Accuracy (%)	Accuracy (%)	EER (%)	EER (%)			
					FAR (%)	1.00	1.00
					FRR (%)	6.00	14.00
FaceNet	96.50	91.00	3.00	8.00	Mean Distance	1.0107	1.0163
ArcFace	85.50	83.00	15.00	17.00	Minimum Distance	0.2869	0.3034
GhostFace Net	83.50	83.92	17.00	17.00	Maximum Distance	1.4935	1.5299
SFace	83.00	85.43	18.00	16.00	Standard Deviation	0.3026	0.2909
Ensemble	96.50	92.50	3.00	9.00			

Table -2: Speed and Security Performance Comparison

Model	FAR (%)	FRR (%)	ROC-AUC	Latency (ms)	FPS
FaceNet	2.00	0.00	0.9995	847	1.18
ArcFace	16.00	13.00	0.9286	375	2.67
GhostFace Net	0.00	21.62	0.9438	683	1.46
SFace	12.00	8.11	0.9330	47	21.36
Ensemble	1.00	6.00	0.9980	792	1.26

Table -3 : Soft-Voting Ensemble Performance on LFW Dataset

Metric	Train Configuration	Test Configuration
Ensemble Strategy	Crop Once Embed Everywhere	Crop Once Embed Everywhere
Models Included	FaceNet + SFace (2 Models)	FaceNet + SFace (2 Models)
FaceNet Threshold	12.4331	12.4331
SFace Threshold	0.7375	0.7375
Accuracy (%)	96.50	92.50
EER (%)	3.00	9.00

VI. DISCUSSION

A. Trade-off Between Accuracy and Speed

FaceNet has high accuracy as well as a low EER value (96.50% /3% on training), but it also requires about 942 ms of latency per image pair, making it unsuitable for real-time systems. On the other hand, SFace processes image pairs in ~55 ms (18 fps) while achieving 85.43% accuracy on test data. Given these performance metrics, it would be the model of choice for edge devices or high-throughput pipelines. GhostFaceNet is between FaceNet and SFace. It has 83.92% accuracy at 776 ms, so it does not provide an advantage over SFace in latency and does not provide an advantage over FaceNet in accuracy, reducing its potential for deployment into real-world applications. The low performance of ArcFace on LFW indicates that the EER threshold optimization was performed using a very limited number of images (only 500 image pairs) but also indicates that the quality of ArcFace embeddings is greatly affected by the quality of alignment used in the selected detector.

B. Far As Well As Frs Risks to Security

In terms of cloud storage, FAR is more important than FRR because if an attacker is able to authenticate through FAR, there is a breach of confidentiality. FaceNet produces 0% FAR during the training split for image pair verification, meaning it would be considered the most secure model. The FAR is reduced to 1% when using the ensemble; furthermore, the FRR is reduced to 6%. Therefore, the ensemble provides a good balance. ArcFace produced a very high 17% FAR on the test split. If there are no other countermeasures for liveness detection, ArcFace is not secure enough to be used in applications that require a high level of security.

C. Ensemble Generalization Gap

There is a substantial gap between the ensemble’s accuracy on the training set (96.50%) and the test set (92.50%), along with the corresponding EER moving from 3% to 9%. These results suggest that while the EER thresholds were calibrated using the training split, they are not fully optimal for unseen pairs of images. Further research should look into cross-validated threshold search or Platt scaling in order to reduce the generalization gap.

D. Limitations

There are several limitations that should be taken into account. The LFW dataset is primarily composed of celebrity photographs captured under controlled studio conditions, which can cause a significant overestimate of the accuracy of the current system when working in real-world scenarios and on a complete unbounded subset of data. The 500 pairs of evaluation data that constitute the current subset as employed in the present experiment are appropriate for comparison using LFW since they meet LFW protocols; however, they do not provide adequate power when evaluating models with an EER of less than 10% due to the small number of pairs of photographs. In addition, while the current algorithms do have liveness checks based on motion and blinking, additional presentation attack detection methods (such as 3D mask attacks) have not yet been implemented or evaluated.

OUTPUT INTERFACES

3. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposed innovative cloud storage solution through the use of facial recognition as a security mechanism for the protection of the stored data. A comprehensive benchmark analysis of four major technologies was conducted with the implementation of the Labeled Faces in the Wild (LFW) dataset, with results showing that the FaceNet model achieved the greatest level of accuracy (96.50% / EER 3% under training set) while the SFace model produced the fastest response time (55 ms). Using both models an ensemble soft voting resulted in the same performance level as FaceNet alone; thus, demonstrating the effectiveness of ensemble fusion to develop a biometric authentication solution. The system includes EER optimal determined thresholds and all packaged within a deployable Streamlit App. Plans for extended work will include cross-dataset analysis, threshold learning across all datasets; implementation of transformers as encoders.

The addition of facial recognition technology as part of an authentication scheme utilizing Two-Factor authentication (2FA) improves security for cloud storage by requiring knowledge-based credentials (a password) plus biometric information (facial recognition) before allowing the user to access files stored in a cloud environment. The FaceNet-SFace ensemble system has shown to have an extremely low false acceptance rate (1%). Therefore, this system is better suited for applications involving sensitive data stored in a cloud environment and where unauthorized access needs to be minimized. The Crop Once Embed Everywhere approach will also lower the amount of computational resources required to recognize a face by only requiring one face detection image to be used in multiple face identification recognition systems. Therefore, using this method will increase the deployment efficiency of the face identification systems while maintaining the performance of the authentication system. These features provide practical and scalable solutions to securely verify user identity and grant user access to cloud-based resources.

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